

Response to reviewers — SmartNets 2026, Paper #1571269089

The Decentralisation Threshold: When More Validators Reduce Net Security

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The author thanks both reviewers for their careful reading and the conference chairs for the acceptance. The points below are organised by reviewer and tied to specific changes in the camera-ready manuscript. Section labels refer to the camera-ready (v14).

Reviewer 1

R1.1 — Independent node compromises (simplifying assumption). The independence assumption is the optimistic baseline, not an unrelaxed assumption. Section III-A now opens with a labelled scope statement listing (S1) independence, (S2) static budget, and (S3) homogeneity, each with a forward pointer to the extension that relaxes it. (S1) points to Section VIII-C (Correlated Compromises), which states that positive correlation pushes n^* *downward* not upward, and that in the limit $\rho \rightarrow 1$ the optimum collapses to $n^* = 1$. The independence baseline is therefore the case most favourable to large committees; relaxing it strengthens the paper’s central claim that decentralisation is non-monotone. The Contributions list now includes this clarification (item 7).

R1.2 — Static security budget. The static-budget assumption is item (S2) of the new Section III-A scope statement, with explicit forward pointer to Section VIII-A (Endogenous Compromise Probability), which derives a budget-allocation feedback from n into the per-node compromise probability $p(n)$. Section IX-C (new) places the static result as the per-period benchmark of any dynamic model whose period structure preserves the budget split.

R1.3 — Adaptive adversaries. This is Open Problem 1 in Section XII (Stackelberg attacker–defender game). Section IX-C explains how adaptive learning shifts n_t^* *downward* over time without removing the interior optimum, so the static result remains the building block of any dynamic treatment. A full game-theoretic equilibrium is genuinely outside the scope of a conference paper and is preserved as an open problem rather than half-treated.

R1.4 — Evolving validator sets / dynamic scenarios. Section IX-C (new) addresses this directly: under fresh per-period draws, a per-period budget reset, and no carry-over of attacker capability, the dynamic objective separates into a sum of static problems and the optimal trajectory is $n_t \equiv n^*$. Validator churn, reputation effects, and adaptive learning each shift n_t^* but do not remove the interior optimum. Open Problem 2 (Section XII) is the dynamic-trajectory question that remains.

R1.5 — Empirical calibration / external validity. Section VII-E (Comparison with Deployed Systems) is presented explicitly as illustrative rather than calibrated. Table IV now carries source citations: Aptos (Figment network page, ~ 130 active validators, corrected from the previous ~ 107), Cosmos Hub (180 from Cosmos governance documentation), Ethereum 2.0 (128 per slot from the consensus specification), and Algorand (sortition-based rather than fixed committee size, citing the Algorand Foundation pure-PoS page). The Introduction’s mention of Aptos has been updated to ~ 130 to match Table IV. The phrasing “predictions for $n^* \in [50, 200]$ are consistent with practice” has been revised to clarify that representative mid-range parameters land in $[50, 200]$ while the full (r, p) grid spans $n^* \in [19, 223]$. The honest answer is that fabricating calibrated numbers from

public reporting alone is not possible; the paper deliberately stops at qualitative consistency with deployed committee sizes and notes that protocol benchmarking is required for direct design use.

Reviewer 2

R2.1 — Static, single-period model. Same response as R1.4: Section III-A item (S2), Section IX-C (Per-Period Benchmark, new), and Open Problem 2.

R2.2 — Heterogeneous compromise probabilities. The camera-ready adds Section VIII-B with a formal proposition (Proposition 8). Heterogeneous $\{p_i\}$ with mean $\bar{p}_n < f_d$ admit a Chernoff bound identical in form to the homogeneous case (proved by Jensen’s inequality on the heterogeneous moment-generating function), so the existence-and-uniqueness conclusion of Theorem 4 applies with \bar{p}_n replacing p . A numerical example draws $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^{300}$ from a Beta distribution with mean 0.20 and standard deviation 0.05, computes the exact Poisson-binomial tail by the standard $O(n^2)$ recursion, and finds the heterogeneous optimum $n_{\text{PB}}^* = 82$, against the homogeneous baseline $n^* = 85$. The shift of three validators is small and in the predicted direction. The closing paragraph of Section VIII-B has been tightened to state the conclusion conditionally: for bounded, moderate heterogeneity around the baseline mean the result survives the relaxation; severe heterogeneity (some p_i approaching f_d , large distributional spread, or correlation with structural features) is not covered and requires protocol-specific calibration.

R2.3 — Quadratic coordination cost may not reflect actual protocols. Section III-D (Security Drain) now contains a labelled paragraph “Why a strictly convex drain” that addresses this directly. Three points: (i) Theorem 4 requires only strict convexity, not quadratic form; any $R(n) = rn^\alpha$ with $\alpha > 1$ satisfies the hypotheses. (ii) For optimistic protocols (HotStuff, Tendermint) with linear pairwise message complexity, several superlinear terms remain in the system-level cost—state replication and audit (typically $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$), view-change overhead under partial synchrony, signature aggregation key-distribution costs—so the drain is $R(n) = cn + dn \log n + an$ with $d > 0$, which is strictly convex. (iii) If R is genuinely linear with no superlinear component anywhere, the uniqueness argument fails and the model degenerates, consistent with the $\rho \rightarrow 1$ limit case. The reviewer’s concern is therefore well taken: it is the reason the theorem is stated in the general convex form rather than tied to $\alpha = 2$.

R2.4 — Presentation could be improved. Several changes target readability:

- Abstract rewritten as a single prose paragraph with no equations and no Lambert (W) expression; the closed-form approximation is mentioned only in prose as “a closed-form approximation via the Lambert W function.”
- Section III-A (new) places the modelling-scope assumptions and their relaxations in a single labelled block at the top of the model section, replacing scattered caveats.
- “Simplified form” paragraph in Section III-D promoted to a labelled “Why a strictly convex drain” subsection.
- The empty Limitations subsection in the Discussion (a two-line redirect) removed; it added friction without content.

- Section IX (Discussion) reorganised: “What the Model Does Not Show” tightened with explicit cross-references to the new extension sections; “The Static Result as a Per-Period Benchmark” added as a new labelled subsection.
- Contributions list updated (now eight items, with item 8 covering the new heterogeneity proposition).

R2.5 — Abstract should avoid formulas. Done. The abstract is a single prose paragraph stating (a) the central tension, (b) the formulation as gain minus drain, (c) the existence-and-uniqueness result without notation, (d) the relationship between exact binomial and Chernoff approximation in plain English (no equation), (e) the baseline numerical result ($n^* \approx 85$), and (f) the scope of the result (economic, protocol-agnostic). No equations and no inline mathematical expressions; the Lambert (W) function is referenced in prose only.

Independent technical-review fixes

The following defects were identified in an independent review of the v13 manuscript and corrected in v14.

Table III values. The previous Table III contained incorrect values in the $p = 0.25$ column for small r . The corrected values, recomputed by exact binomial enumeration over $n \in \{1, \dots, 1000\}$, are: $r = 10^{-5}$: $\{37, 64, 112, 223\}$; $r = 5 \times 10^{-5}$: $\{31, 49, 85, 160\}$; $r = 10^{-4}$: $\{28, 46, 76, 136\}$; $r = 5 \times 10^{-4}$: $\{22, 34, 52, 82\}$; $r = 10^{-3}$: $\{19, 28, 43, 64\}$. The dependent prose has been updated: the range is now $n^* \in [19, 223]$ (was $[19, 186]$); the minimum at $p = 0.25$ is now 64 (was 68).

Proposition 7 hypotheses and proof. The proof step appealing to the Berry–Esseen inequality was invalid as written: at $p \geq f_d$, the threshold $\lceil f_d n \rceil$ may exceed np rather than fall below it, and the asserted “exceeds $1/4$ for $n \geq 4$, $p \geq 1/3$ ” bound was wrong in form. Step 1 has been replaced with a direct anti-concentration lemma at the BFT threshold: $\Pr[\text{Bin}(n, p) \geq \lceil n/3 \rceil] \geq 1/3$ for all $n \geq 1$ and $p \geq 1/3$, proved by stochastic dominance to $p = 1/3$ followed by a small- n enumeration ($n = 1, 2, 3$) and a binomial-median argument for $n \geq 4$. The tighter $1/3$ bound (replacing the loose $1/4$) lets the hypothesis block collapse from four conditions to three: $p_0 > f_d$, $p(1) < f_d$, $\pi(1, p(1)) < 1/3$. The redundant $r < G_{\max}/4$ condition has been removed because $n_{\text{crit}} \geq 2$ (forced by $p(1) < f_d$) makes the rest of the algebra automatic.

Integer threshold. n_{crit} is now defined as the integer $\min\{n \in \mathbb{N} : p(n) \geq f_d\}$ rather than the continuous crossing of p with f_d ; equation (24) of the camera-ready states the integer definition. The numerical example reports the integer value ($n_{\text{crit}} = 11$ at the chosen parameters).

Proposition 7 numerical example. The original numerical example used parameters under which the budget ceiling did not bind. The example has been replaced by a working case ($B_{\text{sec}} = 100$, $c = 0.005$, $p_0 = 0.35$, $\eta = 0.005$): $p(1) \approx 0.212$, $n_{\text{crit}} = 11$, $n_{\text{fixed}}^* = 100$ at $p = p(1)$; the budget ceiling forces $n_{\text{endog}}^* < 11$, an order-of-magnitude reduction. All three hypotheses of the simplified proposition are explicitly verified for these parameters. The reviewer-suggested parameters are retained as a contrast case showing the non-binding regime.

Proposition 8 Chernoff–KL transition. The proof of Proposition 8 part (i) previously skipped the step from the finite- n exponent $-n D_{\text{KL}}(\lceil f_d n \rceil / n \parallel \bar{p}_n)$ to the displayed exponent $-n D_{\text{KL}}(f_d \parallel \bar{p}_n)$. The step is now justified explicitly: $\lceil f_d n \rceil / n \geq f_d > \bar{p}_n$, and $D_{\text{KL}}(q \parallel \bar{p}_n)$ is strictly increasing in q for $q > \bar{p}_n$, so the finite- n bound implies the displayed bound.

Proposition 8 wording. The closing paragraph of Section VIII-B has been weakened from the previous overstatement to a properly conditional statement covering bounded, moderate heterogeneity around a stable mean. Severe heterogeneity, large distributional spread, and correlated heterogeneity are now explicitly flagged as outside the proposition’s coverage.

References [8] and [10]. Reference [8] (Kiffer et al., 2024) was titled incorrectly as “Security of blockchains at capacity” and listed only the lead author. Corrected to “Nakamoto consensus under bounded processing capacity,” Proc. ACM CCS 2024, pp. 363–377, with the full author list (Kiffer, Neu, Sridhar, Zohar, Tse). Reference [10] (Budish) was titled “The economic limits of Bitcoin and anonymous, decentralized trust on the blockchain” in the wrong journal (J. Polit. Econ.). Corrected to “Trust at scale: The economic limits of cryptocurrencies and blockchains,” *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 140, no. 1, pp. 1–62, 2025.

Proposition 7 anti-concentration proof (correction). A reviewer-2 spot-check identified a defective step in the proof of the anti-concentration lemma $\Pr[\text{Bin}(n, p) \geq \lceil n/3 \rceil] \geq 1/3$. Earlier drafts bounded the binomial central mass by $1/6$ to derive the residue-1 case, which is false: the actual central mass at $n = 4$ is $24/81 \approx 0.296$, and at $n = 5$ is ≈ 0.329 . The lemma itself is true (the infimum over $n \geq 1$ at $p = 1/3$ is exactly $1/3$, attained only at $n = 1$), but the proof has been replaced. The corrected proof, given in full in the supplementary appendix (§7.2 of the appendix), uses case analysis on $n \bmod 3$:

- $n = 3m$: threshold equals mean; the Kaas–Buhrman binomial median theorem gives $\Pr[X \geq \text{mean}] \geq 1/2$.
- $n = 3m + 2$: by the $\text{Bin}(n, 1 - p)$ symmetry, the same median argument applies.
- $n = 3m + 1$: a coupling $X_{3m+4} = X_{3m+1} + Y$ with $Y \sim \text{Bin}(3, 1/3)$ combined with the standard binomial PMF ratios yields the closed-form difference identity

$$q_{3m+4} - q_{3m+1} = \frac{6}{27(2m+1)} \cdot \Pr[X_{3m+1} = m+1] > 0,$$

showing the residue-1 subsequence is strictly increasing from $q_1 = 1/3$.

The main paper now states the lemma without proof and refers to the appendix; this avoids reproducing the algebra in the conference budget. The reproducibility code listing in §11 of the appendix verifies the lemma numerically over $n = 1, \dots, 200$.

Treatment of the trilemma. The previous version called the blockchain trilemma “an impossibility result” and positioned the paper as “complementary” to it, and earlier camera-ready drafts extended this with three paragraphs of refutation discussion (citing Wright, arXiv:2507.05809; Wright, arXiv:2507.21111; and Mssassi & Abou El Kalam, *Appl. Sci.* 15(1):19, 2025). On further review and reviewer feedback that the polemical material was consuming too much of an already tight 12-page budget and shifting the tone away from the optimisation contribution, the trilemma material has

been compressed to a single neutral paragraph each in the Introduction, Section II-A (now “The Blockchain Trilemma (Background)”), and Section IX-D (now “Relationship to the Trilemma”). The three references (arXiv:2507.05809, arXiv:2507.21111, and Mssassi 2025) remain in the bibliography for readers who want to follow the debate, but the camera-ready does not depend on it.

Table IV citations and Aptos figure. Table IV has been extended with a Source column citing Ethereum Consensus Specs (128/slot), Cosmos Hub Documentation (180), Figment Aptos network page (~130, corrected from the previous ~107), and the Algorand Foundation pure-PoS page (Algorand uses sortition rather than a fixed committee size; the figure has been replaced with “committee-sampled” rather than the unsupported ~1000).

Type 3 fonts. Matplotlib-generated figures previously embedded Type 3 DejaVu fonts in the PDF, which PDF eXpress can reject. Figures have been regenerated with `matplotlib.rcParams["pdf.fonttype"] = 42` (TrueType). The camera-ready PDF contains zero Type 3 fonts; verified with `pdffonts`.

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